

ORFG Funder Policy Landscape Report and Recommendations: 2026

Executive Summary

An analysis of philanthropic funder policies on open research outputs and open practices

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Open Research Funders Group

<https://www.orfg.org>

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Executive Summary

About the Open Research Funders Group

The [Open Research Funders Group \(ORFG\)](#) is a community of philanthropic funders that seeks to advance open science by increasing sharing and collaboration across the global research enterprise. Members work together to develop policies and practices that can accelerate the pace of discovery, reduce information-sharing gaps, and promote reproducibility. Funders also extend their influence through ORFG by impacting policy, institutions, and furthering dialogues on open research.

Purpose & Scope

In order to better understand current funder policies for open outputs, ORFG analyzed philanthropic funders' access-to-research (or open research) policies. For this report, access-to-research policies are defined as those written policies governing researcher behaviors to make research results readily available, including but not limited to policies requiring or suggesting deposition of narrative results, data, and code into repositories. These policies may also govern rights retention, licensing terms, and more. By understanding the scope of policies, ORFG can identify policy trends and gaps, and assist in the development of strategies to further open practices. This information will also help identify the resources funders need as they socialize and implement open practices and policies within their organizations and among communities, such as grantees, board members, and the general public.

This analysis tracked policy requirements for research outputs and practices, including but not limited to articles, preprints, code, data, data management plans, tangible materials, and more. It did not specifically track book outputs, as very few funders specify books in their policies. The 2026 analysis expanded upon previous analyses and included non-ORFG member funders.

Findings

This analysis and exercise was developed with the understanding that funder policies must serve the approach and strategies of the funding organization. It is important to note that whether or not a funder has a policy does not necessarily signal a lack of interest or commitment to research outputs. Rather, funders employ a wide variety of strategies and approaches to accomplish their goals.

It is also important to note the tension between the dominant publishing models and the ideals of open practices. Funders must support researchers operating in the current research paradigm, yet also have the flexibility and strategic will to experiment with new funding models and open practices.

This analysis included thirty-nine funders, twenty-five of which have policies available for analysis.

Specific findings:

- Funders use a variety of policy approaches to encourage and/or require open sharing of outputs.
- Policies are trending to more often requiring open outputs rather than simply recommending them.
- Adoption of access to article requirements (either open or public access) has increased from 52% in 2023 to 76% in 2026.
- Compared to the 2023 analysis, adoption of preprint requirements has increased by 18%.
- Data deposition is a common requirement, with adoption increasing by 3% since 2023.
- Requirements for data management plans and for data to meet FAIR standards lag behind data deposition requirements.
- There is low uptake on recommendations or policy requirements for persistent identifiers (PIDs), including for funders and awards. Yet there are numerous initiatives and coalitions in the open ecosystem that would enhance or support funder PID adoption. Funders have an opportunity to take advantage of the wealth of knowledge and support that exists in this arena.

Recommendations for Funder Policies

The following five recommendations stem from the analysis and highlight logical next steps for policy improvements and/ or “low hanging fruit” that will support improvements in the open research and open output ecosystem.

1. Eliminate embargo periods

U.S. Federal funding agencies have developed and are currently implementing policies requiring the immediate sharing of research outputs and prohibiting embargo periods. Embargo periods impede the progress of discovery. In a rapidly changing scientific and knowledge production environment, embargos introduce additional barriers to accessing knowledge.

2. Partner with open infrastructure providers

There are numerous initiatives and infrastructure providers that can support funders in implementing open practices. For example, most repositories for data, preprints, and other outputs assign persistent identifiers that can be made openly available and are machine-readable. Using open metadata such as ROR IDs, ORCID iDs, and DOIs would enable better monitoring of funder impacts and research outputs tied to awards as well as enable user discovery. Providers that assign and track PIDs are just one example in this category. Others may include search providers, publishing platforms, preprint servers, licensing standards, peer review communities, Open Educational Resource (OER) tools and more.

3. Expand data management plan requirements and support existing data principles and practices

Data sharing rapidly increases the progress of knowledge and research. Yet without thoughtful sharing that optimizes data discovery and usability, shared data cannot accelerate knowledge discovery. Instead, it may instead lead to wasted effort as researchers reproduce datasets for new analyses. Expanding data deposition policies to support or require the use of FAIR data practices would mitigate the sharing of data that cannot be used in future research due to integrity issues or

other data quality problems. Moreover, supporting the CARE Principles for Indigenous Data Governance will ensure that research data does not perpetuate further harm to indigenous people. Finally, data sharing requirements that translate into adopted practice are most successful when supported by robust training, education, and guidance to support awardees in meeting these expectations.

4. Strategically accelerate preprint adoption

The largest area of growth in funder policy open output adoption is the requirement or recommendation to share preprints. This is exemplified by the existing [Preprint Policy Framework](#) hosted by ASAPbio and created by the Creative Commons Open Science team in collaboration with funders and research-performing organizations. Preprints allow a decoupling of research sharing and research evaluation processes from the commercial publishing enterprise. Moreover, transparent peer review practices, data, and other research output sharing practices are currently being built for the preprint space. Given that the research and information-sharing landscape is rapidly changing in response to both political and technological disruptions, adopting preprint policies - either to replace or complement traditional open access policies - will ensure funders can readily participate in future innovations such as modular science and research sharing.

5. Develop incentives and workflows to complement policy requirements

Policy requirements are one strategy to ensure open practice adoption. However, they should be instituted alongside complementary open practice incentives and workflows. Incentives are also a mechanism that can be used by funders, regardless of whether or not they have codified policies supporting open research.

While some researchers may be motivated by the altruism of open practice, others may be more extrinsically motivated. Introducing extrinsic motivations beyond policy compliance, such as public acknowledgment or commendations for open practices, may further incentivize adoption of open practices. As a complement, workflows that allow for ease of open practice implementation, such as processes for data deposit or compliance and reporting workflows, can signal the need for and support the adoption of open practices.

Next steps

ORFG plans to use this document to encourage implementation and socialization of open output practices and the development of funder access-to-research policies. The report will be publicly shared and socialized to begin conversations in the open output community.

To support funders in implementing recommendations, ORFG will identify, share, and develop the necessary resources.